

MULTISCALE ANALYSIS FOR NEGATIVE THROUGH-THE-THICKNESS POISSON'S RATIO OF ELASTIC-VISCOPLASTIC ANGLE-PLY CFRP LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

In this study, a multiscale analysis for the negative through-the-thickness Poisson's ratio of angle-ply CFRP laminates in the viscoplastic region is performed. First, an angle-ply CFRP laminate with the $[\pm\theta]$ laminate configuration is fully modeled as heterogeneous materials composed of fibers and a matrix. A multiscale elastic-viscoplastic analysis method for the laminate is then proposed based on the homogenization theory for nonlinear time-dependent composites with point-symmetric internal structures. The substructure method is used to enhance computational efficiency. The method proposed is then applied for the analysis of the elastic-viscoplastic Poisson's ratios of angle-ply carbon fiber/epoxy laminates subjected to macroscopic uniaxial tension. The analysis results obtained are used to demonstrate the negativity of through-the-thickness Poisson's ratios in the viscoplastic region and their variation with the degree of viscoplastic deformation.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber-reinforced plastic (CFRP) laminates manufactured by stacking laminae reinforced unidirectionally by long carbon fibers can exhibit negative Poisson's ratios depending on their laminate configurations. This phenomenon was found in the early work by Herakovich [1], in which the Poisson's ratios of angle-ply T300/5208 carbon fiber/epoxy laminates were analyzed using the two-dimensional lamination theory combined with a three-dimensional anisotropic constitutive equation. It was thereby shown that the through-the-thickness Poisson's ratios of the laminates strongly depended on the laminate configuration; the maximum value was over 0.4, whereas the minimum value reached about -0.2 . Clarke et al. [2] also analyzed the through-the-thickness Poisson's ratios of angle-ply T300/913 carbon fiber/epoxy laminates, experimentally confirming the negative Poisson's ratios of the laminates and showing that the negativity depended on the laminate configuration. More

recent research by Harkati et al. [3] has been devoted to evaluating the through-the-thickness Poisson's ratios of three kinds of composite laminates including glass and Kevlar fiber-reinforced plastic laminates as well as a CFRP laminate. According to their results, the carbon and Kevlar reinforced laminates exhibited negative Poisson's ratios, whereas the glass reinforced laminate did not.

The studies mentioned above, however, were limited to elastic analysis. Thus, so far, there has been no report on the effect of matrix plasticity/viscoplasticity on the negative through-the-thickness Poisson's ratios of CFRP laminates. In addition, the previously mentioned studies were based on the lamination theory in which each lamina in the laminates was regarded as a homogeneous elastic material, although laminae are intrinsically heterogeneous materials composed of fibers and a matrix. If this approach is applied to the analysis of Poisson's ratios of CFRP laminates in plastic/viscoplastic regions, the following two problems will arise: (1) a macroscopic elastic-plastic/viscoplastic constitutive equation for each lamina must be constructed three-dimensionally, which is not straightforward because of its remarkably anisotropic and nonlinear behavior; and (2) the approach cannot deal with the microscopic behavior of fibers and a matrix in the laminae, resulting in insufficient understanding of the microscopic mechanisms that determine the negative Poisson's ratios of CFRP laminates.

In this study, a multiscale analysis for the negative through-the-thickness Poisson's ratio of angle-ply CFRP laminates in the viscoplastic region is performed. First, an angle-ply CFRP laminate with the $[\pm\theta]$ laminate configuration is fully modeled as heterogeneous materials composed of fibers and a matrix. A multiscale elastic-viscoplastic analysis method for angle-ply laminates is then proposed based on the homogenization theory for nonlinear time-dependent composites with point-symmetric internal structures [4-7]. The substructure method [7-9] is used to enhance computational efficiency. The method proposed is then applied for the analysis of the elastic-viscoplastic Poisson's ratios of angle-ply carbon fiber/epoxy laminates with various laminate configurations. The analysis results obtained are used to demonstrate the negativity of through-the-thickness Poisson's ratios in the viscoplastic region and their variation with the degree of viscoplastic deformation. Moreover, microscopic mechanisms are shown to interpret the variation in the Poisson's ratios in the viscoplastic region. Finally, microscopic stress distributions in the laminates are discussed in terms of the through-the-thickness and in-plane Poisson's ratios.

2 ANALYSIS METHOD

2.1 Modeling of angle-ply CFRP laminates

Let us consider an angle-ply CFRP laminate consisting of $+\theta$ - and $-\theta$ -laminae, each of which has a thickness of l (Fig. 1). The laminae are composed of carbon fibers and a matrix material. The fibers are assumed to have a hexagonal arrangement in the cross-sectional plane (transverse plane) of each lamina. Each lamina contains 16 (or 15) fibers in the through-the-thickness (stacking) direction in accordance with typical prepreg sheets [7,8]. The laminate is subjected to macroscopically uniform loading, and exhibits infinitesimal strain both macroscopically and microscopically.

2.2 Homogenization theory for time-dependent composites with point-symmetry

For the angle-ply laminate shown in Fig. 1, a unit cell Y can be defined as indicated by the dashed lines in Fig. 1. However, half of Y (i.e., \tilde{Y} in the figure) can also be adopted as an analysis domain using the point-symmetry with respect to the centers of the lateral facets of \tilde{Y} , C_A and C_B in the figure [6-8]. Therefore, in this study, \tilde{Y} is employed as an analysis domain, and is hereafter called a semiunit cell. For \tilde{Y} , the Cartesian coordinates y_i ($i = 1, 2, 3$) are defined (Fig. 1).

Let us first express the microscopic velocity field \dot{u}_i in \tilde{Y} as the sum of the macroscopic and perturbed fields [4-7]:

$$\dot{u}_i = \dot{F}_{ij} y_j + \dot{u}_i^\#, \quad (1)$$

where $(\dot{})$ denotes the differentiation with respect to time t , F_{ij} is the macroscopic deformation gradient, and $\dot{u}_i^\#$ is the perturbed velocity from $\dot{F}_{ij} y_j$. The microscopic strain rate is expressed as follows:

Figure 1: $[\pm\theta]$ angle-ply CFRP laminate, unit cell Y , semiunit cell \tilde{Y} and divided substructures A_α and B_α ($\alpha = 1, 2, \dots, 8$).

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_{ij} = \dot{E}_{ij} + \dot{\varepsilon}_{ij}^\#, \quad (2)$$

where \dot{E}_{ij} and $\dot{\varepsilon}_{ij}^\#$ indicate respectively the macroscopic strain rate and the perturbed strain rate defined as $\dot{E}_{ij} = (\dot{F}_{ij} + \dot{F}_{ji})/2$ and $\dot{\varepsilon}_{ij}^\# = (\dot{u}_{i,j}^\# + \dot{u}_{j,i}^\#)/2$, in which $(\cdot)_{,i}$ represents the differentiation with respect to y_i .

Next, the microscopic stress rate $\dot{\sigma}_{ij}$ in constituents of laminae is assumed to be expressed by an elastic-viscoplastic constitutive equation as

$$\dot{\sigma}_{ij} = c_{ijkl}(\dot{\varepsilon}_{kl} - \beta_{kl}), \quad (3)$$

where c_{ijkl} and β_{kl} represent the elastic stiffness and viscoplastic strain rate of the constituents, satisfying $c_{ijkl} = c_{jikl} = c_{ijlk} = c_{klij}$ and $\beta_{kl} = \beta_{lk}$. In this study, carbon fibers are regarded as elastic materials, meaning that the term β_{kl} becomes zero for the fibers. The matrix material, on the other hand, exhibits viscoplasticity, which plays a dominant role in the nonlinear behavior of CFRP laminates.

The equilibrium of σ_{ij} is then expressed in a rate form as

$$\dot{\sigma}_{ij,j} = 0. \quad (4)$$

The integration by parts and the divergence theorem allow Eq. (4) to be transformed to a weak form:

$$\int_{\tilde{Y}} \dot{\sigma}_{ij} v_{i,j} dY - \int_{\tilde{\Gamma}} \dot{\sigma}_{ij} n_j v_i d\Gamma = 0, \quad (5)$$

where v_i denotes an arbitrary variation of $u_i^\#$, $\tilde{\Gamma}$ indicates the boundary of \tilde{Y} , and n_j signifies the unit vector outward normal to $\tilde{\Gamma}$. The periodicity and point-symmetry of $\dot{\sigma}_{ij}$ and v_i enable the second term on the left-hand side of Eq. (5) to vanish, allowing Eq. (5) to be written as [4-7]

$$\int_{\tilde{Y}} \dot{\sigma}_{ij} v_{i,j} dY = 0. \quad (6)$$

Substitution of Eqs. (2) and (3) into Eq. (6) results in

$$\int_{\tilde{Y}} c_{ijpq} \dot{u}_{p,q}^\# v_{i,j} dY = -\dot{E}_{kl} \int_{\tilde{Y}} c_{ijkl} v_{i,j} dY + \int_{\tilde{Y}} c_{ijkl} \beta_{kl} v_{i,j} dY. \quad (7)$$

The above equation has the following solution for the perturbed velocity field, which is induced independently by the macroscopic strain rate and the microscopic viscoplastic strain rate [4-7]:

$$\dot{u}_i^\# = \chi_i^{kl} \dot{E}_{kl} + \varphi_i, \quad (8)$$

where χ_i^{kl} and φ_i represent functions which are determined by solving the following boundary value problems for \tilde{Y} , respectively:

$$\int_{\tilde{Y}} c_{ijpq} \chi_{p,q}^{kl} v_{i,j} dY = - \int_{\tilde{Y}} c_{ijkl} v_{i,j} dY, \quad (9)$$

$$\int_{\tilde{Y}} c_{ijpq} \varphi_{p,q} v_{i,j} dY = \int_{\tilde{Y}} c_{ijkl} \beta_{kl} v_{i,j} dY. \quad (10)$$

In general, the boundary value problems (9) and (10) are solved numerically using the finite element method (FEM). Thus, they are rewritten here in the finite element discretized form as

$$\mathbf{K} \boldsymbol{\chi}^{kl} = \mathbf{F}^{kl}, \quad (kl = 11, 22, \dots, 31), \quad (11)$$

$$\mathbf{K} \boldsymbol{\varphi} = \mathbf{G}, \quad (12)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\chi}^{kl}$ and $\boldsymbol{\varphi}$ respectively denote the nodal vectors of χ_i^{kl} and φ_i , and \mathbf{K} , \mathbf{F}^{kl} and \mathbf{G} are expressed as

$$\mathbf{K} = \int_{\tilde{Y}} \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{C} \mathbf{B} dY, \quad (13)$$

$$\mathbf{F}^{kl} = - \int_{\tilde{Y}} \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{C}^{kl} dY, \quad (14)$$

$$\mathbf{G} = \int_{\tilde{Y}} \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{C} \boldsymbol{\beta} dY. \quad (15)$$

Here, \mathbf{B} denotes the transformation matrix from nodal displacement to strain, \mathbf{C} indicates the elastic stiffness matrix representing c_{ijkl} , $\mathbf{C}^{kl} = \{c_{11kl} \ c_{22kl} \ c_{33kl} \ c_{12kl} \ c_{23kl} \ c_{31kl}\}^T$, $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ signifies the vector of β_{kl} , and T stands for the transpose.

By substituting Eqs. (2) and (8) into Eq. (3), the evolution equation of σ_{ij} and the relationship between the macroscopic stress and strain rates, $\dot{\Sigma}_{ij}$ and \dot{E}_{kl} , are derived as follows [4-7]:

$$\dot{\sigma}_{ij} = c_{ijkl} (\delta_{pk} \delta_{ql} + \chi_{p,q}^{kl}) \dot{E}_{kl} - c_{ijkl} (\beta_{kl} - \varphi_{k,l}), \quad (16)$$

$$\dot{\Sigma}_{ij} = \langle c_{ijkl} (\delta_{pk} \delta_{ql} + \chi_{p,q}^{kl}) \rangle \dot{E}_{kl} - \langle c_{ijkl} (\beta_{kl} - \varphi_{k,l}) \rangle, \quad (17)$$

where δ_{ij} indicates Kronecker's delta, $\langle \rangle$ denotes the volume average in \tilde{Y} defined as $\langle \# \rangle = |\tilde{Y}|^{-1} \int_{\tilde{Y}} \# dY$, in which $|\tilde{Y}|$ represents the volume of \tilde{Y} . It is noted that $\dot{\Sigma}_{ij}$ and \dot{E}_{ij} are defined as

$$\dot{\Sigma}_{ij} = \langle \dot{\sigma}_{ij} \rangle, \quad (18)$$

$$\dot{E}_{ij} = \langle \dot{\epsilon}_{ij} \rangle. \quad (19)$$

Eq. (19) is derived from Eq. (2) because $\langle \dot{\epsilon}_{ij}^\# \rangle$ vanishes due to the periodicity and point-symmetry of $\dot{u}_i^\#$ on $\tilde{\Gamma}$ [4-7].

The theory described in this section, which has a rate form, is implemented using explicit integration with sufficiently small time increments to perform the computations in the present study. In the computations, $\dot{u}_i^\#$ remains expressed as Eq. (8), and χ_i^{kl} and $\boldsymbol{\varphi}$ are solved independently using Eqs. (11) and (12). Moreover, one-time calculations of \mathbf{K} , \mathbf{F}^{kl} and $\boldsymbol{\chi}^{kl}$ are sufficient because they are not influenced by internal changes. This results in greatly improved computational efficiency in spite of sufficiently small time increments. On the other hand, \mathbf{G} and $\boldsymbol{\varphi}$ need to be computed for every time increments because they evolve with time owing to $\boldsymbol{\beta}$.

2.3 Substructure method

As described in the previous subsection, both the macroscopic and microscopic elastic-viscoplastic behaviors of angle-ply laminates can be analyzed using Eqs. (16) and (17) with the functions χ_i^{kl} and

φ_i . However, solving the boundary value problems (9) and (10) ((11) and (12)) for χ_i^{kl} and φ_i involves numerical difficulty. This is because the semiunit cell \tilde{Y} must be considerably large, as illustrated in Fig. 1, although the analysis domain is half the size of a whole unit cell Y . Therefore, in this study, the substructure method [7-9] is introduced into the nonlinear time-dependent homogenization theory by employing A_α and B_α ($\alpha=1, 2, \dots, 8$) in Fig. 1 as substructures. This method reduces the degrees of freedom of Eqs. (11) and (12) by eliminating components of χ^{kl} and φ with respect to the internal nodes in the substructures, leading to a marked reduction in the computational costs. An explanation of how to introduce the substructure method into the homogenization theory is provided in Ref. [7].

3 ANALYSIS

3.1 Analysis conditions

In the present analysis, $[\pm\theta]$ angle-ply CFRP laminates with 17 laminate configurations, from $[\pm 5]$ to $[\pm 85]$ in 5° increments, were considered. The semiunit cell \tilde{Y} for each laminate was divided into the substructures A_α and B_α ($\alpha=1, 2, \dots, 8$) as illustrated in Fig. 1, which were then discretized into eight-node isoparametric elements. Representative examples of finite element meshes are depicted in Figs. 2-4 for $[\pm 30]$, $[\pm 45]$ and $[\pm 60]$, respectively, each of which has 21504 elements and 23693 nodes. The fiber volume fraction was prescribed to be 56% in each lamina [10,11]. The carbon fibers were considered as transversely isotropic elastic materials, while the epoxy was assumed to be an isotropic elastic-viscoplastic material characterized by

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_{ij} = \frac{1+\nu_m}{E_m} \dot{\sigma}_{ij} - \frac{\nu_m}{E_m} \dot{\sigma}_{kk} \delta_{ij} + \frac{3}{2} \dot{\varepsilon}_0^p \left[\frac{\sigma_{eq}}{g(\bar{\varepsilon}^p)} \right]^n \frac{s_{ij}}{\sigma_{eq}}, \quad (20)$$

Figure 2: Finite element meshes of substructures for $[\pm 30]$ angle-ply laminate.

Figure 3: Finite element meshes of substructures for $[\pm 45]$ angle-ply laminate.

Figure 4: Finite element meshes of substructures for $[\pm 60]$ angle-ply laminate.

Carbon fiber	$E_{LL} = 240$ [GPa]	$E_{TT} = 15.5$ [GPa]	$G_{LT} = 24.7$ [GPa]
	$\nu_{TT} = 0.49$		$\nu_{LT} = 0.28$
Epoxy	$E = 3.5$ [GPa]	$\nu = 0.35$	$\dot{\epsilon}_0^p = 10^{-5}$ [s ⁻¹]
	$n = 35$	$g(\bar{\epsilon}^p) = 141.8(\bar{\epsilon}^p)^{0.165} + 10$ [MPa]	

Table 1: Material parameters of carbon fibers and epoxy [10,11].

where E_m , ν_m , and n are material parameters, $g(\bar{\epsilon}^p)$ is a hardening function dependent on the equivalent viscoplastic strain $\bar{\epsilon}^p$, $\dot{\epsilon}_0^p$ indicates a reference strain rate, s_{ij} denotes the deviatoric part of σ_{ij} , and $\sigma_{eq} = [(3/2)s_{ij}s_{ij}]^{1/2}$. The material parameters of the carbon fibers and the epoxy were set as listed in Table 1 [10,11]. A constant macroscopic tensile strain rate, $\dot{E}_{33} = 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$, was applied to the laminates.

3.2 Results of analysis: Macroscopic stress-strain relationships

Figure 5 shows the macroscopic stress-strain relationships for the representative laminate configurations of $[\pm 30]$, $[\pm 45]$ and $[\pm 60]$ angle-ply CFRP laminates. All laminates exhibit clear nonlinearity due to the viscoplasticity. In particular, the $[\pm 45]$ and $[\pm 60]$ configurations show strong nonlinearity, and the stress level drops markedly moving from the $[\pm 30]$ to $[\pm 45]$ configurations. These results indicate the strong dependence of the elastic-viscoplastic behavior of angle-ply CFRP

Figure 5: Macroscopic stress-strain relationships of $[\pm 30]$, $[\pm 45]$ and $[\pm 60]$ angle-ply CFRP laminates.

laminates on the laminate configuration. In Fig. 5, experimental data for the $[\pm 45]$ configuration [10] are also plotted (open circles) and are in good agreement with the analysis results.

3.3 Results of analysis: Elastic-viscoplastic Poisson's ratios

The relationships between the elastic-viscoplastic Poisson's ratios, ν_{31}^{evp} or ν_{32}^{evp} , and the macroscopic tensile strain E_{33} are shown in Figs. 6 and 7, respectively, for the $[\pm 30]$, $[\pm 45]$ and $[\pm 60]$ configurations, where

$$\nu_{31}^{\text{evp}} = -\frac{E_{11}}{E_{33}}, \quad \nu_{32}^{\text{evp}} = -\frac{E_{22}}{E_{33}}. \quad (21)$$

The elastic Poisson's ratios ν_{31}^{e} and ν_{32}^{e} are plotted at $E_{33} = 0$ in Figs. 6 and 7, respectively. It should be emphasized that, as seen in Fig. 6, the through-the-thickness Poisson's ratio ν_{31}^{evp} for the $[\pm 30]$ configuration is negative not only in the elastic region but also in the viscoplastic region. Moreover, it is surprising that the negativity of ν_{31}^{evp} progressively becomes greater from approximately -0.3 to

Figure 6: Relationship between elastic-viscoplastic Poisson's ratio ν_{31}^{evp} and macroscopic strain E_{33} of $[\pm 30]$, $[\pm 45]$ and $[\pm 60]$ angle-ply CFRP laminates.

Figure 7: Relationship between elastic-viscoplastic Poisson's ratio ν_{32}^{evp} and macroscopic strain E_{33} of $[\pm 30]$, $[\pm 45]$ and $[\pm 60]$ angle-ply CFRP laminates.

-0.65 with an increase in E_{33} . In contrast, ν_{31}^{evp} of the other two laminates are positive and vary little with the increase in E_{33} . In addition, ν_{31}^{evp} of the $[\pm 45]$ configuration is considerably low (i.e., < 0.1).

On the other hand, it is seen from Fig. 7 that the in-plane Poisson's ratio ν_{32}^{evp} is positive in all cases at all strain values. In addition, ν_{32}^{evp} of the $[\pm 30]$ configurations is extremely large, being initially about 1.5 in the elastic region and reaching 2 at $E_{33} = 0.015$. This appears to correspond to the strong increasing negativity of ν_{31}^{evp} for the $[\pm 30]$ configuration mentioned above. It is also noted that ν_{32}^{evp} of the $[\pm 45]$ configuration is moderately large, at approximately 0.9.

In the same manner as described above, ν_{31}^{evp} and ν_{32}^{evp} were examined for the different laminate configurations from $[\pm 5]$ to $[\pm 85]$ with 5° increments. In Figs. 8 and 9, respectively, ν_{31}^{evp} and ν_{32}^{evp} at $E_{33} = 0.015$ are plotted for all laminate configurations (solid circles). For reference, ν_{31}^e and ν_{32}^e are also plotted in the figures (cross marks). Here, $\theta = 0^\circ$ and 90° represent unidirectional laminates in the fiber longitudinal and transverse directions, respectively. In Figs. 8 and 9, steep changes in both ν_{31}^{evp} and ν_{32}^{evp} depending on the laminate configuration are observed, especially below 60° . The peak values (minimum and maximum) are about -1.0 at 20° and about 2.4 at 25° , respectively. It should be noted that, as seen from Fig. 8, ν_{31}^{evp} exhibits negative values in the range between about 15° and 40° , and that it becomes significantly more negative than ν_{31}^e , as already shown in Fig. 6 for the case

Figure 8: Variation of elastic-viscoplastic Poisson's ratio ν_{31}^{evp} depending on laminate configuration $[\pm\theta]$ ($E_{33} = 0.015$).

Figure 9: Variation of elastic-viscoplastic Poisson's ratio ν_{32}^{evp} depending on laminate configuration $[\pm\theta]$ ($E_{33} = 0.015$).

of the $[\pm 30]$ configuration. On the other hand, ν_{32}^{evp} is always positive, irrespective of the laminate configuration (Fig. 9). In addition, ν_{32}^{evp} becomes much higher than ν_{32}^{e} in the range of $15^\circ - 40^\circ$, which is the reversed behavior of ν_{31}^{evp} mentioned above. The difference between the elastic and elastic-viscoplastic Poisson's ratios also depends on the laminate configuration, with the largest value being observed at $20^\circ - 25^\circ$. In contrast, such a difference almost disappears at angles smaller than 15° and larger than 45° .

4 MECHANISMS OF INCREASING NEGATIVITY OF THE THROUGH-THE-THICKNESS POISSON'S RATIO

4.1 Lamina average stresses

Table 2 contains the nonzero components of lamina average stresses in the $+\theta$ - and $-\theta$ - laminae with respect to the y_i coordinates, that is, $\Sigma_{33}^{(+\theta)}$, $\Sigma_{23}^{(+\theta)}$, $\Sigma_{33}^{(-\theta)}$ and $\Sigma_{23}^{(-\theta)}$, for the $[\pm 30]$, $[\pm 45]$ and $[\pm 60]$ configurations. These values were obtained by calculating the volume averages of the microscopic stresses σ_{33} and σ_{23} in each lamina. As seen in the table, for each laminate configuration, $\Sigma_{33}^{(+\theta)}$ and $\Sigma_{33}^{(-\theta)}$ coincide with each other and have the same value as the macroscopic stress Σ_{33} at $E_{33} = 0.015$ in Fig. 5. In contrast, $\Sigma_{23}^{(+\theta)}$ and $\Sigma_{23}^{(-\theta)}$ possess the same absolute value but have the opposite signs. These shear stresses are attributable to the interaction between the $+\theta$ - and $-\theta$ - laminae, and result macroscopically in $\Sigma_{23} = 0$. In the case of the $[\pm 30]$ configuration, the absolute values of $\Sigma_{23}^{(+\theta)}$ and $\Sigma_{23}^{(-\theta)}$ reach about 210 MPa, which indicates a very strong interaction between the laminae. For the $[\pm 45]$ configuration, on the other hand, relatively low absolute values of $\Sigma_{23}^{(+\theta)}$ and $\Sigma_{23}^{(-\theta)}$ are observed (ca. 50 MPa). This indicates that the interaction between the laminae in the $[\pm 45]$ configuration is quite weak. In addition, the near-zero $\Sigma_{23}^{(+\theta)}$ and $\Sigma_{23}^{(-\theta)}$ values for the $[\pm 60]$ configuration imply almost no interaction between the laminae. These results show that the interaction between laminae markedly varies depending on the laminate configuration.

Then, introducing T - L rectangular coordinates by rotating the y_2 - y_3 coordinates with θ (Fig. 10), $\Sigma_T^{(+\theta)}$, $\Sigma_L^{(+\theta)}$ and $\Sigma_{TL}^{(+\theta)}$ are calculated using $\Sigma_{33}^{(+\theta)}$ and $\Sigma_{23}^{(+\theta)}$ (Table 3). It should be noted that

Laminae configuration	$\Sigma_{33}^{(+\theta)}$ [MPa]	$\Sigma_{23}^{(+\theta)}$ [MPa]	$\Sigma_{33}^{(-\theta)}$ [MPa]	$\Sigma_{23}^{(-\theta)}$ [MPa]
$[\pm 30]$	372.5	-211.6	372.5	211.6
$[\pm 45]$	110.5	-49.1	110.5	49.1
$[\pm 60]$	93.4	-5.9	93.4	5.9

Table 2: Nonzero components of lamina average stress with respect to y_i coordinates ($E_{33} = 0.015$).

Figure 10: T - L rectangular coordinates with rotation angle θ for $+\theta$ -lamina.

Laminate configuration	$\Sigma_T^{(+\theta)}$ [MPa]	$\Sigma_L^{(+\theta)}$ [MPa]	$\Sigma_{TL}^{(+\theta)}$ [MPa]
[± 30]	-90.2	462.7	55.5
[± 45]	6.1	104.3	55.2
[± 60]	64.9	28.5	43.4

Table 3: Nonzero components of lamina average stress in $+\theta$ -lamina with respect to T - L coordinates ($E_{33} = 0.015$).

extremely high compressive stress of up to -90 MPa is observed in $\Sigma_T^{(+\theta)}$ of the [± 30] configuration. In contrast, $\Sigma_T^{(+\theta)}$ of the [± 45] configuration is considerably low (ca. 6 MPa), and $\Sigma_T^{(+\theta)}$ of the [± 60] configuration exhibits a relatively high tensile stress of about 65 MPa.

4.2 Microscopic stress distributions

The distributions of the microscopic stress σ_T at $E_{33} = 0.015$ in A_8 , which is the farthest substructure from the interlaminar plane, are depicted in Fig. 11 for the [± 30], [± 45] and [± 60] configurations. It can be seen that there is a very high compressive stress in the T -direction distributed in A_8 for the [± 30] configuration, which results from its high $\Sigma_T^{(+\theta)}$ value listed in Table 3. Such compressive stress can induce positive strain in both the through-the-thickness and fiber-longitudinal directions. However, the carbon fibers prevent the lamina from exhibiting positive strain in the longitudinal direction. Thus, marked positive strain takes place in the through-the-thickness direction, resulting in the negative through-the-thickness Poisson's ratio for the [± 30] configuration. It should be noted that, in the viscoplastic region, the epoxy exhibits more positive through-the-thickness strain than in the elastic region because of viscoplastic deformation. This explains why the negativity of ν_{31}^{evp} for the [± 30] configuration becomes stronger with progressing viscoplastic deformation of the lamina (Fig. 6).

Figure 11: Distributions of microscopic normal stress perpendicular to the fiber, σ_T , in A_8 ($E_{33} = 0.015$).

In contrast, the compressive stress mentioned above is never observed in A_8 for the $[\pm 45]$ configuration, where low tensile stress is distributed (Fig. 11). Moreover, it is seen in Fig. 11 that moderately high tensile stress occurs in A_8 for the $[\pm 60]$ configuration. These stress distributions agree well with the $\Sigma_T^{(+\theta)}$ values in Table 3, and correspond to the near-zero and the positive ν_{31}^{evp} values for the $[\pm 45]$ and $[\pm 60]$ configurations in Figs. 6 and 8.

It is noted that, in each semiunit cell, substructures $A_2 - A_7$ exhibited almost the same stress distributions as that of A_8 . On the other hand, A_1 showed a different stress distribution from those of $A_2 - A_8$, especially around the interlaminar areas.

Herakovich [1] showed that angle-ply CFRP laminates exhibited negative through-the-thickness Poisson's ratios for certain laminate configurations. However, only elastic analysis was performed and the fibers and matrix were not considered separately. In contrast, the present method is able to deal with the viscoplastic behavior of the epoxy. This provides an advantage in the analysis of elastic-viscoplastic Poisson's ratios of angle-ply CFRP laminates. In addition, the near-zero or positive $\Sigma_T^{(+\theta)}$ values found in Table 3 were not reported by Herakovich [1], where it was stated that $\Sigma_T^{(+\theta)}$ was always negative, irrespective of the laminate configuration.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, negative through-the-thickness Poisson's ratios in the elastic-viscoplastic behavior of angle-ply CFRP laminates were investigated both macroscopically and microscopically. This was achieved by fully modeling the angle-ply CFRP laminates with microstructures consisting of carbon fibers and a matrix material. An analysis method applicable to the model was then proposed based on a homogenization theory for nonlinear time-dependent composites with point-symmetric internal structures. Using the proposed method, elastic-viscoplastic Poisson's ratios of angle-ply carbon fiber/epoxy laminates with various laminate configurations were analyzed. In a configuration range between about $[\pm 15]$ and $[\pm 40]$, the through-the-thickness Poisson's ratios exhibited negative values which became increasingly negative as the viscoplastic deformation progressed in the laminates. The increasing negativity was found to be a consequence of the interaction between $+\theta$ - and $-\theta$ -laminae. The interaction brought about marked compressive stress perpendicular to the fiber longitudinal direction in each lamina. This compressive stress acted in the epoxy matrix to induce positive elastic-viscoplastic strain in the through-the-thickness direction. Quantitative validation of the present analysis will be experimentally performed in future work.

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